

EFFECTS OF CURING REGIMES ON MECHANICAL STRENGTH AND DURABILITY OF ALKALI-ACTIVATED LOW REACTIVE VOLCANIC ASHES**J. Baenla****B. Djon****Abstract**

This study evaluated the effects of curing regime on mechanical strength and durability of synthesized products obtained from alkaline activation of two low reactive volcanic ashes. Thus, alkaline activation of volcanic ashes was performed according to three different curing regimes: sealing specimens in polyethylene bags at ambient temperature of the laboratory (SSP25), maintaining specimens in open atmospheric air of the laboratory (SOA25) and oven drying specimens at 60 °C (ODS60). Depending on the raw aluminosilicates and alkali activated products, chemical analysis, SEM (Scanning Electron Microscopy) and XRD (X-Ray Diffraction) were carried out. The SSP25 curing regime favoured high dissolution of phases in volcanic ash but led to low polycondensation due to high water retention, hence synthesized products with low mechanical strength and poor durability. Conversely, ODS60 and SOA25 curing regimes showed great degree of polycondensation which was highlighted respectively by synthesized products with high compressive strength and good stability in acid. Besides, the volcanic ash sample with lowest reactive phase content (18% by mass) demonstrated specimens with high durability in acid medium in terms of mass loss together with increase of residual compressive strength compared to volcanic ash with reactive phase content of 26% by mass. Hence, during alkaline activation of low reactive volcanic ashes, ODS60 or SOA25 were the effective curing regimes for the development of synthesized products with high mechanical strength and good durability.

Introduction

Volcanic ashes are fragments of pulverized rocks which are produced from volcanic eruption. Commonly known as natural pozzolana, they are multi-form particles that possess porous structure and various colours depending on their chemical composition. Chemically, volcanic ash are generally composed of high amounts of SiO₂, Al₂O₃, Fe₂O₃, CaO and MgO oxides making them potential raw materials for the synthesis of alkali or phosphoric acid activated inorganic polymers [[1], [2], [3], [4]]. Their abundance in certain areas in the world allows them to be low cost aluminosilicates destined to the synthesis of eco-friendly cements.

Like other aluminosilicate raw materials, several studies have already revealed interesting outcome of the implication of volcanic ash in the synthesis of alkali activated polymers [1,[5], [6], [7]]. However, some significant differences linked to their reactivity in alkaline medium are observed. Some are very reactive and give alkali activated products with good cementitious properties while the worst is achieved with others [6,8]. These differences are assigned among other to their amorphous phase content and crystalline phases which in return originate from geological formation. In regard with these differences, Djon Li Ndjock et al. (2017) carried out a study on a great number of volcanic ashes which were classified as good or bad precursors in alkali activation [8]. In that study, the authors presented alkali activated volcanic ashes whose specimens possessed almost similar compressive strength values despite the differences that occurred in their respective amounts of reactive phase: volcanic ashes that contained 11.4, 12.5 and 42.5% by mass of reactive phase, expressed compressive strength of 1, 1 and 1.1 MPa respectively after 14 days of curing in polyethylene bags at ambient temperature of the laboratory [8]. Curiously, volcanic ash with reactive phase content of 42.5% by mass was normally expected to perform greater mechanical strength as compare to the others. Using volcanic ash whose reactive phase content was 46% by mass, Djobo et al. (2016) obtained compressive strength of 8 MPa with specimens cured for 7 days at ambient atmosphere of the laboratory [9]. In addition, Tchakoute et al. (2013) obtained compressive strength of 19 and 50 MPa respectively in alkali activation of volcanic ashes whose reactive phase contents were 34.8 and 64.8% by mass for specimens aged 28 days and cured at ambient temperature of the laboratory [6]. The aforementioned mechanical strength variations were largely dependent on both curing conditions and chemical composition of reactive phase. Several authors have revealed the contribution of various curing conditions in the synthesis of alkali activated polymers. Among many there exist: water curing, temperature (oven) curing, open air curing, CO₂ curing and seal curing in a polyethylene bag [[10], [11], [12], [13]]. Temperature (oven) curing is mainly applied in alkali activation of slow reactive aluminosilicate raw materials [[14], [15], [16]]. High temperature curing (60–80 °C) was found to be more relevant than ambient temperature in the development of cementitious properties of alkali activated products. Zeyad et al. (2022) reported that the reaction rate of volcanic pumice dust – cement kiln dust in alkaline medium is more sensitive to high temperature (65 °C) [15]. According to Djobo et al. (2016), high temperature (60 and 80 °C) curing of volcanic ash based alkali activated materials increases the dissolution of reactive species and enhances the mechanical properties [9]. After further investigation, Djobo et al. (2016) also showed that no matter the high 28 days compressive

strength expressed by volcanic ash based alkali activated materials cured at 80 °C, the latter expressed higher loss of mass and compressive strength when immersion in 5% sulphuric acid solution for 180 days compared to those cured at ambient temperature [17]. For Alomayri et al. (2021), the temperature of 60 °C for 24h is the adequate curing regime for synthesis of slag based alkali activated material containing 10% of rice husk ash. The authors revealed in addition to the high compressive strength, the latter material expressed the least loss of mass and strength when exposure in acid and sulphate solutions separately for 120 days [14]. In the art of alkali activation of aluminosilicates, sealing of specimens in polyethylene bags at the atmosphere of laboratory is the most used [6,8,9]. However, this type of seems to be beneficial only for alkaline activation of certain aluminosilicates [[18], [19], [20]]. According to Lee et al.(2016), sealed curing at ambient temperature of laboratory is more appropriate to fly ash based geopolymers than unsealed one [18]. The reverse is true according to Xie and Kayali [21]. Depending on the chemical composition of raw materials, water management in the reaction medium has an impact on cementitious properties since its consumption in alkali activation is low as compared to common hydraulic cements [9,22]. In alkali activation of inorganic polymer, water is considered as a chemical component in which at the end of polycondensation stage, a certain quantity might be retained in the network of alkali activated gel or participates in the formation of hydrated binding phases while the rest is released [[23], [24], [25]]. It is well known that the quantity of water retained in alkali activation is proportionate to the amount of reactive phase and other reactive constituents present in the reaction medium. According to some investigations, in fly ash based geopolymers, about 10.74 % by mass of the whole water used is retained by the alkali activated polymer gel [25] whereas in metakaolin based geopolymers, the latter is found to be around 17.00% by mass [26]. It is well known that metakaolin is the precursor possessing the highest content of reactive phase [27,28]. So, water content in gel phase of the alkali activated product must be related to the amount of reactive phase in the precursor. On the contrary, if water content is too high, the latter may have tremendous effects on the cementitious properties of alkali activated products. For instance, high water to solid mass ratio hinders the polycondensation stage, hence decreases mechanical strength [26,29]. Recent studies showed that optimum properties of some alkali activated materials can be achieved by applying intermittent water curing [10,13]. According to El-Hassan et al. (2021) 2 days in water followed by subsequent air curing (25 days) of slag-fly ash based alkali activated concrete containing 25% by mass of fly ash produces optimal mechanical properties while with equal mass of slag and fly ash, continuous water curing (27 days) is required [10]. In the art of alkali activation of

aluminosilicates, there exists no standardized curing regime. Thus, determination of suitable curing regime in alkaline activation may allow appreciating the intrinsic reactivity of aluminosilicate raw materials and by this way, the best or the worst mechanical properties along with durability of synthesized products. To the best of our knowledge, there exists no study done on the effects of curing regime in alkaline activation of low reactive volcanic ash. The present study investigates the suitable curing regime necessary to get best mechanical strength and long durability of alkali activated low reactive volcanic ashes. To this end, specimens from alkali activation of two volcanic ashes were subjected to three different curing regimes: sealing specimens in polyethylene bags at ambient temperature of the laboratory (SSP25), oven-drying specimens at 60 °C (ODS60) and maintaining specimens in open ambient atmospheric air of the laboratory (SOA25). The resulted products were submitted to characterization tests such as compressive strength, durability, X-ray diffraction, thermal analysis and scanning electron microscopy.

The two low reactive volcanic ashes were collected along the “Cameroon Line” [30] and were denoted respectively as Ma and Vn. Prior to be used, they were oven-dried at 105 °C, pulverized using ball mill and later on sifted thanks to the use of a 100- μ m sieve. The alkaline activating solution resulted from mixing sodium hydroxide solution (12 M) and commercial sodium silicate with respect to SiO₂/Na₂O molar ratio of 1.4 was used. According to Djobo et al. (2016), the dissolution reactive species

Raw materials characterization

The chemical compositions of volcanic ashes are given in Table 2. Both precursors are almost composed of the same oxides and the sums (SiO₂ + Al₂O₃ + CaO) are respectively (% by mass) 66.96 (Ma) and 69.21 (Vn). These oxides are necessary for alkaline activation if ever found in amorphous phase of the precursors [6,9]. Loss on ignition (%by mass) in Ma is 1.79 and is almost twice in Vn (3.87). This discrepancy may suggest the presence of more hydroxylated phases in Vn than in Ma. Moreover,

Conclusion

The use of low reactive volcanic ash as alone raw material in alkaline activation seems of low interest due to its low reactivity in alkaline medium. This study tries to provide curing regimes necessary to enhance the mechanical properties and durability of alkali activated low reactive volcanic ashes. The following conclusions can be drawn:

Sealing curing regime in a polyethylene bag fosters phase dissolution but hinders polycondensation reaction due to significant retention of water molecule

References

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